

UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS

School of Earth and
Environment

CASTLETON MAPPING PROJECT

Field Report (Dissertation)

Lukas Starkevicius

SID: 201437464

January 2024, Leeds, UK

Word Count: 7458

Abstract

Castleton is located in the Peak District, at the margin of the Last Glacial Maximum ice sheet. The area provides access to the geological history from the Carboniferous era, including Carbonate, Clastic Rocks to peri – glacial deposits. The report presents a detailed geological mapping study of the Castleton area. A geological map was produced with various supporting data such as cross sections and sedimentary/carbonate logs, that helped to unravel and create an evolutionary ground model of the area.

The oldest rocks make up 2 different Carbonate Reef Systems: the older Winnats Reef and the younger Pindale Reef. The Beach Formation which was mapped at the foot of Winnats Pass is of high interest in this field study. Its depositional submarine flow nature offers a potential origin of Winnats Pass. The change of depositional environments due to regional subsidence led to the shutdown of Carbonate Reefs and resulted in the deposition of deeper water Odin Shale Formation and turbiditic sandstone Mam Tor Formation. Quaternary geology includes Dry Valleys and Loess that were created by peri – glacial activities, as the proto-Castleton area was at the border of the Last Glacial Maximum ice sheet but was not covered by the glacier itself. The Mam Tor Landslide is the most recent feature on the map, as it is active to this day. Mineralization is in the form of fracture – hosted mineral veins and hydrocarbons that precipitated in carbonate rocks. The mineral veins consist of fluorite, baryte and occasionally galena.

Overall, the study reveals the geological history of Castleton since the Carboniferous and confirms the origins of Winnats Pass and the Beach Formation.

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1. Introduction

The methodology of our study included the systematic geological mapping of the field, to construct an in – depth understanding of the Castleton geology. A write – up phase followed, that aided in producing a presentable report of analysed field data, comparing it to the available literature. ArcGIS, CorelDraw, Stereonet and SediLog were utilised in a digitisation stage to create presentable figures for the report.

The field report was undertaken in the Castleton area, Derbyshire (*Fig. 1.1*). The main aims of the study included constructions of the geological map, cross – sections, different rock unit descriptions and their interpretations of depositional environments, a geological history, an overview of mineralization and quaternary geology in the area, based on the observed evidence. Specific interest was taken in the Beach Formation deposits and their depositional origin together with Winnats Pass based on the crinoidal depositional orientation in the outcrops, which was followed by a statistical approach to prove the quality and relevance of the data. A discussion comparing our report’s results with published studies is presented in *section 7*.

1.1 Aerial Map of the Castleton Area

Castleton area

2. Core of the Report

2.1 Geological Map of the area

2.2 Stratigraphy Column

2.3 Cross Sections

2.3.1 Pindale Quarry (A1-B1)

2.3.2 Winnats Pass (A2-B2)

2.3.3 Mam Tor (A3-B3)

2.4 Lithological Descriptions

Winnats Reef System

2.4.1 Winnats Farm Formation (WFF)

Most of the outcrops were observed at the top of the Winnats Pass and Cave Dale but they are also widely scattered in the southwestern area of the map. In the south, it borders a unit from another reef system – Upper Pindale Limestone Formation (UPLF), in the east - northeast it borders Treak Cliff Formation (TCF) with the exceptions of Winnats Pass and Cave Dale, where the unit is in contact with Winnats Gentle Formation (WGF). The north boundary is with the Odin Shale Formation (OSF) and due to the lack of outcrops, it was fully projected based on the secondary features (drainage patterns, vegetation, topographic depressions). Weathered outcrops are light grey, fresh are lighter grey/white. They are dominantly wackestones, less common – packstones (according to the Dunham Classification Scheme). The beds are horizontal, wavy, highly shattered (intensely weathered), mostly not prominent and hard to follow, but a few exceptions of less weathered outcrops allowed to observe that the thickness of the beds varies from 10 cm to 50 cm. Fossils are not common, crinoids and brachiopods were observed but much smaller compared to WGF. *Lithostrotion junceum* corals had been identified close to the boundary with the WGF at the top of Cave Dale (Figure 2.4.1).

Figure 2.4.1. *Lithostrotion junceum* corals at the top of the Cave Dale. Visean age (N.H. Museum).

2.4.2 Dale Basalt Beds (DBB)

Outcrops were located at the top of the Cave Dale, where they overlay the WFF, and some not in situ boulders were located down the Longcliff (GR 142280 825810). The weathered outcrops are brown dominant, fresh surface is darker brown. Vesicles up to 2 cm wide were observed, the outcrops at the Cave Dale contain vesicles with calcite fillings.

2.4.3 Winnats Gentle Formation (WGF)

The outcrops are located in the Winnats Pass and Cave Dale areas. The unit mainly borders the TCF and WFF from 2 different reef sides. The weathered colour of the outcrops is light grey, fresh is lighter grey/white. The outcrops vary from limestone wackestones to packstones (occasional grainstones were observed), beds are wavy and hard to follow (not prominent), and their thickness is highly variable from a few cm up to 40 cm, usually with a dip up to 15° westwards/south-westwards but at places the beds are horizontal. Fossils of crinoids, brachiopods and corals were observed. Crinoids are well – preserved but randomly orientated. Brachiopods are common in the unit, only

Gigantoproductus has been identified. *Rugose* and *Bryozoan* corals were identified. See the field carbonate log for a more detailed section from the WGF and the distribution of the fossils in Cave Dale in a vertical section of 4 meters (Fig. 2.4.2). The largest rugose coral was found in Cave Dale as well, it was 3.3 cm wide (Fig. 2.4.3).

Figure 2.4.2. Carbonate log from locality 282 (GR 414893 382385).

The WGF can also be identified using the depositional direction of crinoids. In this case, the depositional orientation of crinoids is rather random, but some clusters do indicate a dip direction of the unit beds. *Figure 2.4.4* shows the crinoidal orientation data, which is rather scattered but a cluster towards the southwest exists (circled in red) and potentially indicates the dip direction of the bed, as crinoids would have fallen there and kept the orientation due to the gravity.

Figure 2.4.3. *Dibunophyllum bipartitum* rugose solitary coral observed in the unit, located in the Cave Dale transect. Visean – Namurian Age (*N. H. Museum*).

Figure 2.4.4. Stereonet with crinoidal orientation data from *locality 288* (GR 415026 382479), plotted as lines using trend and plunge measurements. Clustered area potentially indicating the dip direction of the bed is circled in red.

2.4.4 Winnats Top Formation (WTF)

The outcrops of this unit were only located in the Winnats Pass and Cave Dale areas. The outcrops are always disconnected from each other and act as enclaves inside of the WGF and WFF. The weathered surface of the outcrops is dark grey, fresh is light grey. The outcrops are limestone mudstones, contain no bedding, no fossils were observed except at the boundaries with the TCF and WGF.

2.4.5 Treak Cliff Formation (TCF)

The longest unit of the area with its outcrops located from the north of Pindale Quarry to the southern border of the Mam Tor Landslide. The weathered surface of the outcrops is light/dark grey, fresh is light grey except for outcrops in the Pindale quarry which exhibit brown weathered surfaces. Outcrops vary from limestones of wackestones to grainstones (dominantly packstones), and dip from 20° to 30° towards NNE. The beds are intensely wavy and not prominent, with thicknesses from 10 cm to 80 cm (occasionally thicker beds up to 2 m were observed). See the short carbonate log in Cave Dale to see variations of different beds (*Fig. 2.4.5*). Fossils of brachiopods and crinoids are

Figure 2.4.6. *Gigantoproductus* brachiopod in the TCF unit, located in the Cave Dale.

Figure 2.4.7. Stereonet with crinoidal orientation data from locality 275 (GR 416098 382332), plotted as lines using trend and plunge measurements. Clustered area potentially indicating the dip direction (N) of the bed is circled in red. Note the location is close to Pindale Quarry, where the beds show a more northern orientation. The reading of this locality is 112/27 N.

2.4.6 Beach Formation (BEF)

Beach Formation rests locally unconformably on the TCF, located in the East of Winnats Pass and West of the Castleton and is overlain by the OSF. In the south, the formation is bordered by the TCF, in the north – boundary with the OSF was observed. The weathered colour of the outcrops is dark grey, fresh is light grey. The outcrops are made up of limestones varying from packstones to grainstones, beds dip 18° – 20° east with a thickness of 40 – 60 cm. Crinoids and brachiopods are abundant and well preserved, *Gigantoproductus* were observed. The crinoidal orientation tends to be highly clustered and shows an approximate depositional orientation of east – west (see Fig. 2.4.8).

Figure 2.4.8. Stereonet with crinoidal orientational data plotted as lines using trend and plunge measurements from locality 21 (GR 413849 382773)

2.4.7 Boulder Formation (BF)

The Boulder Formation is mainly located around the Odin Mine, where the outcrops are scattered on top of the TCF, mostly as boulders. Outcrops consist of grainstone limestones, have no bedding and are made up of mixed limestone mudstones and grainstones. Windy Knoll outcrops contain Neptunian Dykes, that were also described by Trevor (1996). The weathered colour is light grey, fresh is light grey. The outcrops contain many randomly orientated crinoids (see Fig. 2.4.9 below for a stereonet) with brachiopods, most of them poorly preserved and highly disarticulated.

Figure 2.4.9. Stereonet with crinoidal orientation data plotted as lines using trend and plunge measurements from *locality 85* (GR 413382 383471), shows a random distribution.

Pindale Reef System

2.4.8 Lower Pindale Limestone Formation (LPLF)

Outcrops are located in Pindale Quarry and around its areas. In the west it has a projected boundary with the UPLF and in the northeast – a boundary with the TCF. The weathered colour of the outcrops is blue/dark grey, whilst fresh is light grey. Rocks are dominantly wackestones, seldom mudstones, bedding is mainly horizontal with a few beds dipping west up to 10° . The beds are somewhat wavy and highly prominent with thickness varying from 10 cm to 150 cm. Fossils of crinoids and brachiopods are not as abundant as they are in the UPLF, and they are much smaller in size (up to 2 cm long). *Lithostrotion* colonial corals were observed.

2.4.9 Dirtlow Boulders Beds (DLB)

The outcrops are located in the southwest of the Pindale quarry. It consists of grey and black matrixes with white quartz minerals. The matrixes appear to be non-reactive with an HCl acid. Crystallized fossils are present within the grey matrix with very fine quartz – looking minerals.

2.4.10 Upper Pindale Limestone Formation (UPLF)

Located just northwest of the Breedon Hope Cement Works quarry, the unit is a part of the youngest reef system in the area. It has projected boundaries with the WFF and TCF, it is partially overlain by the DLB. The weathered rocks are blueish – dark grey to brown, fresh surfaces vary from white to light grey. The outcrops vary from wackestones to grainstones but are dominantly packstones, contain horizontal bedding. Beds are easy to follow, very prominent with thickness being from 10 cm to 150 cm. When compared to the LPLF, brachiopods and crinoids are more abundant, larger and less disarticulated in the UPLF. Potential evidence for stromatolites is also observed in the carbonate log of the unit (*Fig. 2.4.10*). Outcrops are also characterised by often containing clusters of grainstones with large ~ 10 cm long crinoids and no corals being present.

Figure 2.4.10. Carbonate log from locality 197 (GR 412820 381097).

Clastic Units

2.4.11 Odin Shale Formation (OSF)

Odin Shale Formation unconformably overlays both reef systems in the Castleton area and is overlain by the Mam Tor Formation (MTF). In the south, east and west of Castleton, shale overlays the TCF with an exception in the west of Castleton, where shale overlays the BEF. Further northeast of Castleton, the OSF is overlain by the Mam Tor Landslide and in the north – northwest of the map it is overlain by the MTF. South of Mam Tor, there is an area of the OSF which is disconnected from the Shales in the east. Outcrops are black to dark grey, clay and silt – grained, extremely breakable, contain <1 mm wide shiny micaceous and are horizontally bedded. Rarely it contains fossils of goniatites *Gastrioceras carbonarium* (observed at *locality 184*), brachiopods and pieces of petrified wood with leaves. Goniatites might be an indicator of the marine bands. As the formation contains very few outcrops, most of the boundary locations were determined by secondary features such as breaks in the slope, drainage patterns, unique spiky dry vegetation, presence of streams and topographic depressions (see Fig.2.4.11).

Figure 2.4.11. Schematic sketch from the field showing how topographic depressions form in limestones. Such features would not be found in shale or sandstone as only limestone is dissolvable.

2.4.12 Mam Tor Formation (MTF)

The MTF conformably overlays the OSF, is up to at least 90 m thick, outcrops show horizontal bedding with the bed thickness being highly variable from 2 cm to 2 m, sandstone beds are laterally extensive. The outcrops are located in the northwestern part of the mapping area, where boundaries with the OSF and the Landslide were found. Generally, the formation comprises of interbedded shales and sandstones, with shale being more dominant in the lower parts of the formation and sand dominant in the upper parts, a few erosional surfaces are observed between shale and sandstone. Shale is black to dark grey, clay and silt – grained, extremely breakable with <1 mm wide shiny micaceous. Shale is identical to the OSF, but no fossils were observed. Sandstone is well sorted, fine to coarse (dominantly medium coarse), light brown to grey, with flute marks on the base (see *Fig. 2.4.12*) indicating paleocurrent direction towards the southwest. See the 16.5 m long sedimentary log of the Mam Tor (*Fig. 2.4.13*).

Figure 2.4.12. Flute Marks observed at Mam Tor locality 185 (GR 412980 383722)

Figure 2.4.13. Sedimentary log from locality 185 (GR 412980 383722).

2.5 Depositional Environments

Winnats Reef System

Figure 2.5.1. Depositional model for the Winnats Pass reef system. Lagoonal facies represent Winnats Farm Formation, back reef – Winnats Gentle Formation, algal reef – Winnats Top Formation, fore reef – Treak Cliff Formation.

2.5.1 Winnats Farm Formation

The depositional environment of the formation is a lagoonal setting (*Fig 2.5.1*). The main indicators are the tiny crinoids and wackestones which suggest a very low energy environment. The beds are also quite horizontal which is characteristic of lagoonal facies. The potentially observed *stromatolites* (see *Fig. 2.4.10*) also suggest a low energy lagoonal depositional environment as the modern day *stromatolites* are found in the lagoonal or saline lake settings (*Bowlin et al., 2012*).

2.5.2 Dale Basalt Beds

The main evidence of the depositional environment is the vesicles, which suggest that lava formed as an extrusive basalt potentially during a regional extension. The filling of the calcites must have come from the limestones which were deposited on top of the DBB. Calcites raise the hypothesis that the basalt was formed during the deposition of the WFF in a lagoonal setting, as it would explain where the calcite is coming from, but no lava pillow structures were observed, which leaves the hypothesis that the basalt could have formed above the water as well (subaerial extrusion).

2.5.3 Winnats Gentle Formation

The depositional setting of this formation is in the back reef of the carbonate reef system (*see Fig 2.5.1*). The opposite dip (mainly towards the west) relative to the dip of the TCF is the main indicator of the depositional setting, but well – preserved fossils, abundant brachiopods and the presence of *Rugose* and *Bryozoan* corals suggest a lower energy environment full of marine life which is highly characteristic to the back – reef facies (*Webb, 2002*).

2.5.4 Winnats Top Formation

The depositional setting of the WTF is the core of the reef system (*see Fig 2.5.1*). The core is where the reef grows and is often referred to as an algal reef. No presence of fossils and the presence of limestone mudstones are the main evidence of this hypothesis. As the outcrops consist of mudstone, it also indicates a low energy environment and an intense diagenesis. During the deposition, the outcrops must have been in shallow water settings where the surrounding energy is high. Limestone mudstones are deposited in a low energy setting and the presence of the outcrops in the current day suggests that the rocks must have formed fast to preserve themselves.

2.5.5 Treak Cliff Formation

The depositional setting of the TCF is the fore reef of the reef systems (*see 2.5.1*). Steep dips and their direction are the main evidence of such deduction, abundant debris of crinoids indicate that they had fallen from higher places of the reef as they are randomly orientated (*see Fig. 2.4.7*) and highly disarticulated. Well – preserved brachiopods indicate that they had fallen not long after their demise, having their muscle systems to keep the shelves intact.

2.5.6 Beach Formation

Figure 2.5.2. Depositional model for the Beach Formation. The potential submarine flow cutting through the Winnats Pass Reef System and depositing the Beach Formation at the low areas of the Treak Cliff Formation.

The BEF is interpreted to have a depositional environment of a submarine fan/flow, that cut through Winnats Reef Facies (*Fig 2.5.2*). The incision we see at Winnats Pass today was likely caused by this flow and then enhanced by peri glacial streams that created dry valleys in Quaternary. The 3 pieces of evidence support the depositional setting of the BEF:

1. The elevated geomorphology of the BEF contains a form of a fan as it was deposited in the manner of an alluvial fan (*see Fig 2.5.3 below*). It is the reason for the formation name.

Figure 2.5.3. Digitised schematic field sketch, showing a depositional nature of the Beach Formation at Winnats Pass. It was deposited in an alluvial fan manner by a potential submarine flow.

- East – west depositional orientation of the well-preserved crinoids. After their demise, the crinoids were carried down by the submarine flow, the medium – lower energy environment of the flow kept the crinoids preserved and orientated to the flow direction. See *Figure 2.4.8* for the stereonet data. *Figure 2.5.4* shows how crinoids are deposited by a submarine flow and can keep their paleo depositional setting which also indicates a paleocurrent direction for a submarine flow.

Figure 2.5.4. Digitised schematic field sketch, showing how orientation of crinoids is preserved during the deposition by a submarine flow.

- The BEF outcrops contain lots of well - preserved *Gigantoproductus* brachiopods (see *Fig. 2.4.6* but note that the particular brachiopod is from the TCF unit). These brachiopods were brought down by the submarine flow not long after their demise mainly from the back reef/lagoonal depositional facies, which led to brachiopods still maintaining their muscular system and hence keeping the shells intact. A greater water depth and the nature of the submarine fan also contributed to the preservation of brachiopods as there were fewer predators in the area.

Overall, there is a lot of uncertainty about the depositional environment of the BEF, but current evidence suggests that they were formed by a higher – energy submarine flow, that started at the top of the carbonate reef.

2.5.7 Boulder Formation

The depositional environment of BF unit is of a submarine avalanche origin. The boulders likely started forming at the top of the carbonate reef in the core reef (WTF) low energy environment as mudstones, where they would form as carbonate moulds. Potentially due to the earthquakes, the moulds would break down and start falling to the depths of the fore reef (TCF) higher energy environment, where they would mix with fossils and grainstones. See *Figure 2.5.5* below for a depositional model of the BF.

Figure 2.5.5. Digitised schematic field sketch, showing the potential deposition of the Boulder Formation.

2.5.8 Lower Pindale Limestone Formation

The depositional environment of this unit is interpreted to be of a back reef system. It is evidenced by the wackestones, which indicate a low energy environment and by the *rugose* corals which are characteristic of the back reef facies. The observed dip of up to 10° of the outcrops to the west also indicates a back reef depositional setting as it correlates geographically with a reef system in the area. The unit is hypothesised to contain core reef facies, however, no outcrops of algal reef were observed leaving this hypothesis uncertain. Refer to *Figure 2.5.1* for the depositional environment of the Winnats Pass reef system, as the Pindale reef system was also deposited in the same conditions.

The Pindale reef system is proposed as a younger reef system when compared to the Winnats Pass reef system. The main evidence is observing the back reef facies of both reef systems at different levels. The LPLF ones are outcropping at approximately 250-300 meters above sea level, whereas the WGF outcrops at 200-250 meters. It shows that the Pindale system is topographically higher and hence stratigraphically younger than the Winnats system. The other less certain evidence is observing the UPLF wall relics at *Hurd Low* (GR 413800 381800), on top of the WFF. However, it is highly uncertain if the walls are of the Pindale System as they are not in situ and were moved around a lot.

2.5.9 Dirlow Boulders Beds

The grey and black matrixes are silicified limestones. All the carbonates had been replaced by silica. The likely environment of such silicification could have come from silica – rich sources such as hot springs or sponges. Hot springs are a more viable explanation as the basin was exposed to extensional regimes (more about it in *section 4. Geological History*), but to conclude, there is simply too little evidence to fully support this hypothesis.

2.5.10 Upper Pindale Limestone Formation

Well – preserved crinoids indicate a lower energy environment and crinoidal grainstone clusters show the richness of life during the deposition of the unit. No presence of corals rules out the depositional environment of a back reef, leaving the lagoonal setting as the best fit depositional environment as the beds also are horizontal. See *Figure 2.5.1* for the carbonate reef depositional model.

2.5.11 Odin Shale Formation

Clay and silt particles that consist of shales indicate a low energy environment. The dark colour and scarceness of the fossils indicate anoxic conditions. The fossils observed in the shale did not live on the ocean floor where the shale was initially being deposited. A few found goniatites are pelagic animals and presumably fell to the ocean floor after their demise. Brachiopods are benthic animals and were moved to the deep ocean due to storms or falling off the continental slope from the coastal areas, this can be applied to petrified wood and leaves that are found in the OSF. Petrified wood and leaves indicate that the coast and delta were plant – rich. All the above suggests the depositional environment of the formation of a very low energy, anoxic, deep ocean (abyssal plain) environment. The presence of micas indicates the lithological immaturity suggesting that sediments had not been transported far from their source. The source of unit sediments could have been derived from the

metamorphic rocks such as Lewisian Gneisses which at the time were part of the eroding Caledonian Mountains in the north of Castleton area. See *Figure 2.5.6* below for a depositional model of the OSF. Note that shale was being deposited both in the OSF and MTF. The only difference is that the MTF contains turbidite deposited sand interbeds.

Figure 2.5.6. Depositional model of Odin Shale and Mam Tor Formations. Note the underlying relics of carbonate reef system and the deposition of shale covering both Mam Tor and Odin Shale Formations areas.

2.5.12 Mam Tor Formation

The depositional environment is an anoxic, low energy, deep ocean where shale was being deposited with a frequent input of coarser material (later to become sandstones) via high energy turbiditic flows from the southwest as indicated by flute marks (see sedimentary log in *Fig. 2.4.13* for azimuth values of flute marks). The sandstone and shale interbeds suggest a frequent high energy change from low to high. The fact that the OSF is overlain by the MTF suggests the seacoast regression and an increase in the sediment supply probably eroding from the Caledonian mountains and brought by the rivers to the ocean (see *Fig. 2.5.7* below). The progradation led to the formation of turbidites which resulted in interbedded deposition of sandstones and shales.

Figure 2.5.7. Schematic sketch proposing that we start seeing the Mam Tor Formation overlaying the Odin Shale Formation due to increased sediment supply and prograding seashore.

3. Mineralization in the area

The mineralization in Castleton was observed in the forms of hydrocarbons and fracture – hosted mineral veins. Minerals are of Mississippi Valley Type (MVT). The evidence of hydrocarbons and all the mineral veins was observed in Carbonate Rocks, none in Clastic units. The fractures and mineral veins depict 2 separate geological events:

1. Strike – slip faulting which caused fractures.

Fractures were formed by strike – slip faulting during the deposition of Carbonate Rocks. A relatively same orientation of the faults (*Fig. 3.1*) suggests that the fractures were forming in the same event that had a rotating stress regime (the distribution of faults is in a 30° radius). The presence of strike – slip faulting proposes an extensional setting, that occurred due to proto-Castleton being in the back – arc basin (*see Section 4 for more details*).

Figure 3.1. Stereonet with strike slip fault orientational data, plotted as planes. The orientation is roughly WSW – ENE and covers 30° of azimuth.

2. 2 different origin fluids

The mineralization event for mineral veins in the area must have occurred at any point after the shale's first diagenesis. The shale worked as a seal rock to keep the fluids inside the carbonate rocks, where the ore – bearing fluids, migrating via faults, reacted with carbonates and precipitated the minerals. The mineralization dominantly consists of fluorite, baryte, occasionally galena and were likely precipitated from hydrothermal fluids.

Hydrocarbon fluids indicate different origin fluids, that were as well deposited after the deposition of the OSF that acted as a seal. The evidence of hydrocarbons is observed at Windy Knoll (*GR 412622 383012*), surrounded by the WFF lithology. Given the hydrocarbon fluids nature in the pressurised environment, we would expect to see them only at the top of carbonate reef systems, which acted as a trap rock. This can be confirmed by the Edale No. 1 oilwell (*J. Gluyas et al., 1938*), which was located in the north of the mapped Carbonate Reef Systems, where no hydrocarbons were found.

A review by *Ford and Worley (2016)* confirms the presence and provides detailed explanations for both hydrocarbons and MVT mineralization in the Castleton area of South Pennine Orefield.

4. Geological History

1. Deposition of Winnats Reef System in a shallow marine environment (Lower Carboniferous).

The 1st unit to start forming was the WTF as its depositional setting was a core of a reef system. The TCF and WGF must have started forming a bit later, but once the system evolved, all 4 units (WTF, TCF, WGF and WFF) were being deposited simultaneously. The relative sea level must have been gradually increasing to create accommodation space for the reef to grow (Fig. 4.1). The reef system must be at least of Lower Carboniferous Age as *Lithostrotion junceum* (Fig. 2.4.1) were observed and they are of Visean age (Natural History Museum, 2012).

Figure 4.1. Schematic sketch showing the relative sea level increase creating accommodation space for a reef to grow.

The observed strike – slip faulting in the Winnats carbonate rocks suggests that faulting could have started as early as the formation of the Winnats Reef System. From the regional geological history, it is known that the Caledonian Mountains formed from Ordovician to Early Devonian in the north of Castleton, as a response to the Rheic Ocean closure (P. Stone BGS et al., 2015), which resulted in the creation of the back – arc regime in the proto – Castleton area. The back – arc basin kept getting wider and deeper due to the bend of the Avalonia plate and the thermal subsidence from the weight of the Caledonian Mountains. All the strike – slip faults in the area are attributable to the back – arc extension, which also resulted in the continued subsidence of the area.

2. Formation of the Beach and Boulder Formations (Lower Carboniferous).

The exact timing of the formation of these units is hard to determine given the lack of available data but based on the depositional settings of the units, the BF started forming as short recurrent events earlier before a single longer event which formed the BEF. The BEF was observed as a later feature of Winnats Reef System as their depositional paleo submarine flow had incised all the carbonate units of this system. No observed outcrops in the Pindale Reef System of both BEF and BF suggest the depositional timing of the formations during the deposition of the Winnats Pass System.

3. Change in a sea level led to the formation of a new different Pindale reef system.

A highly uncertain event which is presented by 2 different hypotheses:

- Global sea level drop and the creation of extra accommodation space by subsidence during the extensional regime period kept the relative sea level stable. The sea level dropping must have increased and started lowering the relative sea level. The extension that was creating extra accommodation space was caused by the back – arc regime. As the relative sea level was dropping it led to the relocation of a new Pindale reef system.
The drop of the relative sea level must have been short in the geological time, due to observed thick bedded Pindale reef units which suggest a rapid reef growing pace as it had to keep up with the rising sea level.
- Another hypothesis suggests no sea level drop, only a fast rise due to the combined effects of the global sea level increase and subsidence. This rise relocated the new reef closer to the shore where the relative sea level was smaller and viable for a reef formation. This hypothesis agrees with the 1st hypothesis on a rapid sea level rise due to the observed thick beds in the Pindale reef system. The regional subsidence in this case was the main contributor to the relative sea level rise.

Overall, 1st hypothesis seems to fit better, as the initial sea level drop explains why we observe some of the Pindale reef outcrops topographically lower than Winnats Pass reef, where naturally we would be expecting all the Pindale reef system to be topographically higher as it is proposed as a younger reef system (*section 2.5.8*). However, there is no direct evidence for the global sea level drop as proposed in the 1st hypothesis.

4. Deposition of the Pindale Reef system (Lower Carboniferous).

Includes the formation of the TCF of the Pindale system, LPLF, UPLF and DBB. The Pindale Reef system created an unconformity with the Winnats Pass system. The deposition of the Pindale reef system was fast due to the observed thick beds as previously discussed. The extension was still occurring during this period as the strike slip – faults were still observed in the Pindal Reef system.

5. Uplift and Erosion that resulted to erosion mainly of the Pindale Reef System (Mid – Carboniferous).

Another event with very little evidence but it must have occurred as the Pindale Reef System is not observed on top of the Winnats Pass and Cave Dale areas where the Winnats Pass reef system is present. The event most likely was triggered by an intensive sea level drop.

6. Subsidence into very deep levels of the depositional environment of Odin Shale Formation (Upper Carboniferous).

The continued thermal subsidence of the back – arc basin in Castleton resulted in the formation of horsts and grabens environment (potentially due to bend faults), which created the thermal sag basin, was the main source of the relative sea level rise. After the erosional period of the reef systems, it led to the complete cessation of the Carbonate reefs and

introduced the deep water low energy shales to the area, which created an unconformity with the Carbonate systems.

The hydrocarbons and fracture – hosted mineralization must have occurred sometime after the 1st diagenesis of shale as it was acting as a seal rock for both fluids to keep them entrapped. The exact timing of each mineralization is unclear based on the current evidence, same as their comparable depositional age.

7. Deposition of Mam Tor Formation (Upper Carboniferous).

Due to the increasing sediment supply from the eroding Caledonian Mountains, seashore progradation occurred as the sediment supply surpassed the available accommodation space. As the seashore was prograding, coarser sediments were being brought closer to the proto – Castleton area, which eventually led to the deposition of high energy turbiditic flows full of sands. The flows were periodic and not constant, so during the quiet periods of no sand deposition, low energy clays were still being deposited (refer to *Fig. 2.5.7* for a depositional sketch), what resulted in interbedded shales with sandstones in the MTF.

8. Uplift and erosion to present – day topography, excluding quaternary geology and a landslide (Permian to Neogene).

The subsidence ceased and the global sea level started dropping which led to long erosional periods.

9. Deposition of Loess and Dry Valleys (Quaternary).

The quaternary features in Castleton are all periglacial. They include loess, dry valleys and cave systems that were created during the last ice age period when the Castleton area was just outside of the glacial extent, but not covered by the glacier itself.

10. Mam Tor Landslide (Holocene)

The youngest geological feature on the map, the landslide initiated around 3600 years ago (Skempton, 1989). The extent of it was mapped primarily using the brackens as they tend to grow where the land had been disturbed.

5. Quaternary Geology

The last time Castleton was covered by the glacier was in the Chibanian (*Hornyak, 2020*) ice age. During the Last Glacial Maximum, Castleton was not covered by the glacier, but it was located nearby (*Fig. 5.1*) (*Bowen et al., 2002*) and the quaternary deposits seen in Castleton were formed during this period (26,000 – 19,000 years ago). The main features of quaternary geology in the mapping area are Loess and Dry Valleys, but it also includes cave systems and the Mam Tor Landslide. Here we will discuss the features of Dry Valleys and Loess.

Dry Valleys

There are several dry valleys in the Castleton area (see the geological map in *section 2.1*) with the largest one being in Cave Dale. In Castleton, they started forming during the last ice age from the melting ice of the glacier surfaces. The melt would form these glacial streams and create highly sinuous, river – like structures. The water would not sink there, as the ground was under the permafrost conditions, not letting the stream reach limestone and dissolve it. All the dry valleys in Castleton indicate a rough orientation of west – east, which suggests that the paleo flow came from the west, as that is where the closest glacier was located to Castleton (*Fig. 5.1*).

Figure 5.1. Map of the British Isles, showing the Last Glacial Maximum extent with an annotated location of Castleton.

©base map created by Andy Emery, 2020 (personally modified)

Loess Deposits

Loess are the terrestrial clastic soil deposits, mainly consisting of silt – sized particles, which are usually formed by glaciers grinding down the rocks into silt particles, which later are accumulated and deposited by the wind – blown dust (*Muhs et al., 2013*). In the Castleton area, loess formed by glaciers is observed, it is light brown and very silty, potentially with a low percentage of clays. After glaciers compressed the rocks to silts, those fine particles were transported away to the west potentially by the same periglacial streams that formed dry valleys (see *Fig. 5.2*). Once the periglacial streams lost its energy, the loess would be carried and deposited by wind.

Figure 5.2. Schematic sketch, showing how loess in Castleton area formed and was carried by stream and wind forces.

6. Statistics for the Beach Formation

This section introduces simple mathematical evidence that the data taken from the crinoids in the BEF outcrops is not random or diverse, and different data locations have relatively the same mean direction. Due to the hypothesis that the BEF formed as a submarine flow with NNE direction, crinoidal depositional orientation will be considered directional data, showing the flow direction. See *Figures 6.1 and 6.2* for rose diagrams showing the paleo flow from 2 separate outcrops that are analysed statistically below.

Location 21

Important data for the statistical analysis:

- Mean direction ($\bar{\theta}$) = 87.4
- Resultant length (R) = 9.88
- Mean resultant length (\bar{R}) = 0.9877
- Circular variance (α) = 0.01
- Concentration Parameter (K) = 50.25
- Number of data samples (n) = 10

Figure 6.1. Rose diagram showing the deposition of crinoids orientational data (azimuth) from the BEF, locality 21 (GR 413849 382773)

Tests for randomness

Using the test of mean resultant length (Rayleigh's Test), where \bar{R} calculated (0.9877) > \bar{R} critical (0.576), therefore data is not random and has a preferred orientation.

Using a *Chi-squared* method, where the rose diagram is divided into 12 equal segments, $x^2 = 52.61$ (calculated value) and $v = 19.675$ (critical value), $x^2 > v$, therefore the data is not random.

Distribution Test

Using Von Mises distribution test, where the concentration parameter (K) from the mean resultant length (\bar{R}) table = 50.25. As the concentration parameter (K) is very high, the data is clustered and not dispersed.

Hypothetical mean direction (one sample) test

$$S_e = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n \times R_{mean} \times K}} = 0.0449 \text{ radians}$$

$$1.96 \times S_e = 0.088004 \text{ rads} = 5^\circ$$

$$\text{Mean direction } (87.4) \pm 5 = 92.4^\circ \text{ and } 82.4^\circ$$

Observed mean lies within the hypothesised the BEF depositional direction of NNE, therefore it is from the specified mean direction.

Location 178

Important data for the statistical analysis:

- Mean direction ($\bar{\theta}$) = 13.2
- Resultant length (R) = 4.79
- Mean resultant length (\bar{R}) = 0.9586
- Circular variance (α) = 0.04
- Concentration Parameter (K) = 12.77
- Number of data samples (n) = 5

Figure 6.2. Rose diagram showing the deposition of crinoids orientational data (azimuth) from the BEF, locality 178 (GR 414239 382617)

Tests for randomness

Using the test of mean resultant length (Rayleigh's Test), where \bar{R} calculated (0.9586) > \bar{R} critical (0.754), therefore data is not random and has a preferred orientation.

Using a *Chi-squared* method, where the rose diagram is divided into 12 equal segments, $x^2 = 30$ (calculated value) and $v = 19.675$ (critical value), $x^2 > v$, therefore the data is not random.

Distribution Test

Using Von Mises distribution test, where the concentration parameter (K) from the mean resultant length (\bar{R}) table = 12.77. As the concentration parameter (K) is very high, the data is clustered and not dispersed at all.

Hypothetical mean direction (one sample) test

$$S_e = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n \times R_{mean} \times K}} = 0.1278 \text{ radians}$$

$$1.96 \times S_e = 0.1278 \text{ rads} = 7.3^\circ$$

$$\text{Mean direction } (13.2) \pm 7.3 = 20.5^\circ \text{ and } 5.9^\circ$$

Observed mean lies within the hypothesised BEF depositional direction of NNE, therefore it is from the specified mean direction.

Are both data sets coming from a population with the same mean directions?

The test is performed by comparing individual sets resultant lengths (R_{21} and R_{178}) with the combined resultant length (R_T).

$$R_{21} = 9.88$$

If $R_{21} + R_{178} \approx R_T$, then means are close.

$$R_{178} = 4.79$$

If $R_{21} + R_{178} \gg R_T$, then means are different.

$$R_{21} + R_{178} = 14.67$$

$$R_T = 12.10$$

As $14.67 \approx 12.10$ ($R_{21} + R_{178} \approx R_T$), the means of the sets are similar.

Test for equality of mean directions (using F-statistics), are the samples from populations of the same mean direction?

$$R_{21} = 9.88 \quad F_{calc.} = \left(1 + \frac{3}{8K}\right) \frac{(n-2)(R_{21} + R_{178} - R_T)}{(n - R_{21} - R_{178})} = 113.896918$$

$$R_{178} = 4.79 \quad v_1 = 1$$

$$R_T = 12.10 \quad v_2 = 15 - 2 = 13$$

$$\bar{R}_T = 0.8064 \quad F_{crit.} = 4.67$$

$K = 3.00020$ *If $F_{crit.} > F_{calc.}$, then populations have the same mean direction.*

$n = 15$ *If $F_{crit.} < F_{calc.}$, then populations have different mean directions.*

$$F_{crit.} > F_{calc}$$

As $F_{crit.}$ is larger than the $F_{calc.}$, the samples have a general the same mean direction.

Conclusions

By using statistical methods above, it has been demonstrated that the crinoidal depositional data from the BEF contains a preferred direction, is clustered, not random and when compared to data from the other location (*loc. 178*), relatively the same mean direction was deduced.

7. Discussion

Winnats Pass and the Boulder Formation

Winnats Pass is a gorge – type feature, located in the northwest of Castleton. Its incision lets us observe the relationships between different facies of Winnats Reef System and the BEF but the origins of the pass itself are debatable. The data from our study suggests that Winnats Pass was incised by the submarine flow that formed the BEF and during the Quaternary, the pass was deepened by the periglacial streams (*Section 2.5.6*). A past study (*Ford, 1987*) considers a few stages that led to the current Winnats Pass:

1. Depositional hollow between the 2 reef systems in Winnats Pass (*also suggested by Southern et al., 2014*).
2. Scour channel that produced the BEF (a submarine flow) during low sea levels period (*also suggested by Southern et al., 2014*).
3. Uplift in middle Carboniferous (*Section 4, event no. 5*), that led to an erosional channel in Winnats Pass and the creation of the BF.
4. Deepening by periglacial streams in Quaternary.

Our study has found evidence that supports events no. 2, 4 and partially no. 3. An origin of the submarine flow (no. 2) is evidenced by the consistent crinoidal depositional orientation, and the morphological elevation seen at the foot of Winnats Pass (*Sections 6 and 2.5.6*). The presence of dry valleys in the area supports event no. 4 (*Section 5*). An uplift for event 4 is considered in the report (*Section 4*), but it has no direct evidence and should be only partially considered. No evidence was found in the field to support stage no. 1. The mapping in Winnats Pass did reveal that an agal reef is observed on both sides of the incision which led Ford to believe that there were 2 separate reef systems forming close to each other, but no presence of fore reef facies inside the gorge (in the middle) suggests a single large carbonate system.

Ford (1987) and *Simpson (1969)* also suggested that the BF is a younger feature than the BEF, formed due to the uplift in mid – Carboniferous. Simpson argues that subaerial erosion features of solution surfaces were observed at Windy Knoll between the BF and WFF, that would suggest a subaerial origin of the BF, however, no such features were observed at any of the BF outcrops in our study. Our study argues that the BF was forming periodically, triggered by earthquakes and overaccumulation at the tops of the Winnats Reef System, making it older than the BEF.

Cessation of Carbonate Reefs and Clastic Sedimentation Origin

The field report hypothesises the continued thermal subsidence, due to the back – arc rifting which led to deep water levels, was the main factor for the shutdown of Carbonate Reef Systems (*Section 4, event no. 6*). These deep water levels hosted a depositional environment for the OSF. *Southern et al (2014)* agrees with our hypothesis of the shutdown and specifies that the carbonates experienced a drowning unconformity. It suggests the water levels after the Carbonates cessation being as deep as 500 m, however, due to the presence of immature micas, the depth must have been not as deep (likely around 200 meters).

Our study agrees with *Southern et al (2014)* that sediments forming the OSF and MTF were derived from the Caledonian Mountains in the north of proto – Castleton. Turbiditic origin of the MTF and their appearance in the area due to the increased supply of sediments are agreed upon.

Change from Winnats Reef System to Pindale Reef System

As suggested in *Section 4 event no. 3*, a change in the sea level led to the depositional change from Winnats Reef to Pindale Reef. 1st hypothesis proposes a sea level drop for the reef to relocate and then a sea rise, as thick – bedded fast growing Pindale reef beds were observed. The timing and chain of events correlate with the South Pennine Orefield genesis study performed by *Quirk (1987) (Fig. 7.1)*. He suggested an anticlockwise stress field rotation that started towards the end of Visean. By the late Visean, the shifted stress fields started causing compression in the area, which resulted in the development of a regional fold and a major uplift in Castleton. The subsidence reappeared in the area again by the early Namurian. This major uplift coincides with the drop in the sea level proposed by our study, which initiated the drop to begin with, and resulted in the formation of the Pindale reef system. The subsidence in the early Namurian corresponds with the 2nd part of our hypothesis, which states that increased subsidence led to a fast-growing reef.

Figure 7.1. Table with Quirk's and our study's events for correlation

Quirk (1987) event	Age	Our study event	Age
Compression and uplift	Late Visean	Change from Winnats Reef system to Pindale system	Lower Carboniferous
Major Subsidence	Early Namurian	Fast growing Pindale Reef	Lower Carboniferous

8. Conclusion

The mapping study revealed 2 different carbonate reef systems (Winnats Pass and Pindale). It was deduced that the younger Pindale system was overlaying the Winnats system in the past. The Winnats Pass incision itself was deduced to have formed mainly due to the submarine flow that was forming the BEF, the gorge was enhanced by periglacial streams during the Quaternary.

Mapping of the OSF and MTF raised the hypothesis of continuous subsidence due to the back – arc lifting, caused by the Caledonian Orogeny, which led to the shutdown of the Carbonate systems and changed depositional environment to deeper water shales. Turbiditic sandstones were followed due to the coast progradation (increased sediment supply).

Quaternary and mineralization features were mapped and described. Shale was deduced as a seal rock for both hydrocarbons and fracture – hosted mineralization and without deposition of shale, we would not be observing any mineralization in the area. Quaternary deposits of Loess and features of Dry Valleys were formed during periglacial activities, the Mam Tor Landslide is the most recent geological feature in Castleton.

Overall, many uncertainties remain in the geological evolution of the area, but the extensive mapping offers a new detailed geological map of the Castleton area and new data supporting the submarine flow origin of the BEF.

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